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Transcript

Speaker 1

So it's a record. Yes. Hello, my name is Anna Makarubi. I'm pursuing a master in software engineering at the Blagan Institute of Technology. And my thesis is investigating how developers and maintainers perceive vulnerabilities in offensive dependencies, including their projects, especially considering the rise of supply chain attacks that have been frequent in recent years. And I'm focusing on five web frameworks, Django, Next.js, Spring Boot, Larafield, and Ruby on Rails. And participation in this research is entirely voluntary. You can withdraw from the end of it anytime. You will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Your name, role, e-mail address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip questions they're not comfortable answering, and your responses will remain anonymous and not be linked to the projects that you represent. The interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisors to verify authenticity of the reporting data after which they'll be deleted. And we follow GDPR guidelines. So that's it. Okay, so we'll start before You can introduce yourself and the project, the web framework that you use, your experience level with the framework. Also, how many years you've been in the software development industry. You can tell us also whether you're a developer using the framework or you're also a contributor or maintainer in project.

Speaker 2

I'm working as a software engineer and it's been 14 years. I'm working on Ruby on Rails. So Rails is the framework, Ruby is the language. And I worked on different projects from small scales to large scale with different domains. So yeah.

Speaker 1

So the projects that you work on, are they commercial or open source?

Speaker 2

No, no, they were confidential. It wasn't the open source.

Speaker 1

And in those projects, do you use like other framework, like maybe JavaScript or strictly?

Speaker 2

Yes, for front end, we have used JavaScript with the backend technology, which is Ruby on Rails. And mostly for me, I have been using like JavaScript mostly on front end with HTML and on back end Ruby on Rails.

Speaker 1

And for the projects that you worked on, was there a security team responsible for security or it was left through the development team?

Speaker 2

Actually, the framework itself handles a lot of security things. Like if you the Rails framework, they have inbuilt facility for major security attacks that we know. So it is inbuilt in the Rails. We don't have to worry about all those things. But when it comes to writing the code, you have to be Like you cannot develop the website where you, you're not providing, say, so there are different roles, right? So you have to, you cannot show things which admin should see and the other person with other role they should not see. So that's also like information. So that level of security that developer needs to handle. like the login has to be proper, their passwords needs to be stored properly. And even for passwords like the login management trails also have a good gem, which is the library, the devise library, they handle it properly. Like for if you include that library and follow certain steps, they have handled it for us that the password should be encrypted and how it should be which encryption should be applied and all. So all the best Practices that library has already taken care of we just have to integrate that, so a lot of things in Rails has like you can say major things which a person shouldn't need to worry about has handled by the framework itself. But when it comes to the developer, we have to be careful of what information we are showing to which user and all these things have developer has to take care like who needs what access and say certain pages needs authentication. So do you have the authentication? Like if you're trying to open certain page, if you're trying to modify the URL, with different numbers like you're trying to access it through URL changes. So all these things if your developer has to take care of like while writing the code like you're fetching the data properly and while fetching you're not showing unnecessary information in the API details. Like whenever someone is like even accessing the APIs, you are not sending the. too much information or some information which is secret should not be shared. So this

level has to be taken care of by the developer and yeah, by the mostly like is being handled by the Rails framework.

Speaker 1

Alright, and do you add additional dependencies when working with the Rails framework or you usually just stick to the ones that come with the framework?

Speaker 2

No, like it depend on the requirement, like what exactly is your requirement adds, but that you add the dependence. Like if you want the payment gateway, like you have certain things in your application where you're doing payments, you need to handle the payments. So you cannot develop the payment gateway and everything by yourself. So you include the library. So that's a dependency. Now that library itself has handled everything for payment. So It's not that I will go and implement for every transaction. If it fails, it should revert back. So everything has been taken care by that particular library. We just know how to integrate that with your code.

Speaker 1

OK. So when we are using-- we are integrating those dependencies into your project. How conscious are you of the dangers that they might present to your projects in case they become vulnerable?

Speaker 2

Sorry, can you come again?

Speaker 1

Okay, so sometimes dependence we use in our projects can have some security vulnerabilities within them. So I'm asking how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependence present to your projects?

Speaker 2

Yes, so we do regular updates. of the library. So if you have included any dependency, they themselves like release a node, like release a new version, like what are the things they have fixed or there is an issue. So you have to keep an eye on the news and of that particular library, like what maintenance are saying. Say they have said like, okay, there is some issue that they are seeing and they're working on it. So you go to this version. This version is has some bugs. So you revert back to the previous version and you continue doing do your work. So once you know that okay, that issue has been fixed by the

maintenance of that particular library and. everything is good and they have given the go ahead that okay everything is fixed what exactly issue was everything details are there. So you just upgrade your the version whichever is like updated in your project. So how we handle the dependency is by upgrading and you do like as I said like Rails framework itself will warn you that okay certain libraries are not compatible you need to upgrade. And if you are upgrading and you have to keep your project updated with the current versions of your software. So you cannot stay on the lowest version of that particular, say, Rails and you continue working on it. So you will not have support for that old libraries and old versions. You have to keep updating your software. Timely, not regularly. I would say say well was after like six months you should have update on your project like you're updating it to the latest version. Then in six months you continue your development again. You see, OK, are there any major changes happened into the libraries that we are using? If yes, and do we need those features? Do we need certain things? Then only upgrade. So it's then become like upgrade becomes one of the maintenance tasks that you have to do. Okay.

Speaker 1

And how are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects, especially the fact that the dependencies in your projects can lead to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

I never worked on any project related to supply chain, so I can't comment on that.

Speaker 1

And then how do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your projects? Are there any tools that you use to monitor your dependence to see whether they are still safe?

Speaker 2

Yes, there are libraries provided by Rails like the Brakeman. And so when you do bundle install, even it will show you that certain versions are not compatible. And even on the GitHub itself, like if you have your project, there are some settings that you do that shows like if there is a vulnerability and then that you need to address. So there are different ways that you get to know about it. Okay.

Speaker 1

How do you check the maintenance of the dependency in your project just to see whether the creators of the dependents are still maintaining? Or once you install it, you don't check whether it's still being maintained.

Speaker 2

Like once we get the updated versions, I mean, I did not get the question.

Speaker 1

Okay, so sometimes people create open source projects and then they stop maintaining them, like they abandoned them, right? Mm-hmm. They need in your project. So how do you check that the dependence you're using is still getting updates?

Speaker 2

In that case, yes, yes. Yes, so there are many libraries like that in Rails where maintenance are not maintaining it since last four or five years. So if you have used a certain library which is for handling roles, role management or accessibility management, now that particular library is not maintained for, say, five, six years, you know that it is outdated. It will not work with the latest versions of your current code. Then there definitely there would be definitely some alternative libraries that people are using. If you don't find any alternative, what you have to do, you have to fork that particular library and you have to maintain it for your project. So you then you make a choice like whether you want to, you know, publish it to the people that you have updated it and you are maintaining it now or you can keep it as a private code of your project, maybe you have some code in that particular library which is related to your project. Like now you have using it as your code and you have certain things like, you know, sometimes you modify things which are related to. So these libraries are public. They don't have you just have to plug it to your project, but certain libraries. If there are internal libraries, we don't have them as a separate entity. There are some dependencies on each other, like you need to, some variables are defined, say some classes are used commonly like that. So it depends on your project requirement, like how you handle it. But in that case, you have to maintain it by yourself or find an alternative.

Speaker 1

I'm glad that you mentioned taking over a project if it's no longer being maintained. And I understand that you, okay, how difficult is that when that dependence is no longer will be on Rails? Maybe it's a JavaScript dependent because that can also happen with JavaScript dependence that they are no longer being maintained.

Speaker 2

Yes, mostly if it is a popular library, people will have some alternatives. the it is because see if it is not maintained means there are some reasons like maybe not many people are using it or there are better alternatives faster ways has been developed using latest technology and there is an alternative solution to it but some people they already have

included that particular library and it is the code is now working as you know with respect to that library now if they have to you know replace that library and take the new library. They have to make many changes inside the code. Suppose they have to make many changes and it is extra work. They might not take that call immediately. to shifting to the new, they might consider to maintain the old library by themselves for certain time. And then when they make a decision that, okay, now we are at the stage where they don't have any customer deliverables which are like priority and they got some time for maintaining and doing some upgrades of the software. So when you have, you got the time, you have the employees free time, then be some companies take the decision that okay, we'll include some companies take this. So this decision matters on the project, like how many people are there, how important it is at the moment, is it necessary, like immediate, because some companies have large, large amount of employees, so they can take this decision faster, like they will say, okay, replace it today itself. Because they have employee, they have strength to take that particular time. But if the company is small, like say 5-6 people are there, they can't take this decision immediately. They have to find a time where they can do this upgrade so that other customers will not get impacted if something goes wrong. Because if you're doing something upgrade code wise, there will be chances some unknown bugs will come, some blockers will come and you will get blocked. You don't know for a week or month or no. So they don't want that the customer should get impacted because of certain things. They want to test it thoroughly. So it totally depends on what is your requirement and when you decide to maintain the old library or you decide to shift to the new library.

Speaker 1

Alright. Okay. Do you have any particular guidelines you follow when you are deciding to use a dependence within your project?

Speaker 2

But dependency like guidelines for including new. Yes. So if you cannot like say there are 10 employees, I cannot go and find out, okay, this library is very cool. Let's include it. Like for say JavaScript, there are many cool libraries available and like button can be looked like this, look like that. You know, some libraries can make it more interactive, but you cannot take that decision by yourself. Like, okay, I like this library, I'm including it. See, there are small, small libraries also, like I can't give you an example, say charts for charts, like there are some libraries which will show very fancy charts, some libraries will show a decent chart. So you cannot just go and, okay, I need this, I like this library and I'll include it. You have to take the decision company-wide. I'm thinking of including this library, why I think we should include, you should have whys clear and what are the pros and cons of current

thing and what are the pros and cons of new thing. So when you come up with those pros and cons and why we need, why we need to add these, why some people just certain tasks that you can do it by yourself, but some people prefer it to use the library. But if you use the third party dependency, then that comes with the challenge that if some that person is not going to maintain and what if that you left the job and that person now that library somebody has to learn like how to include it and it's an unnecessary headache. So it is a conscious decision by the team that what we are including in our project. So while including you definitely check like if it is a well maintained for many years, has many stars, and it's not a buggy code because you cannot guarantee like some codes are with no bugs and all. So it just will break your system if it is not developed properly. So you will definitely go with the libraries which are used by many people since many years. And if you are trying to include something new, that has to be there with some reasons like, okay, why we are including it. And what is the strong reason behind that?

Speaker 1

Okay. So in other words, you would rather build the functionality yourself first before you consider building the functionality first before you consider using independence.

Speaker 2

Hmm.

Speaker 1

Okay. And OK, do you face any challenges trying to address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Not at the moment because we have been using very popular, well maintained libraries. But I have not come across of any dependency which had like too much issues like OK, it's very difficult to maintain and. include and how to sometimes fix like nobody's fixing or maintaining that library know what to do. So there there is not much experience that I have got that yeah, but I have seen.

Speaker 1

OK. And what makes it easier for you to address these vulnerable dependencies in your within your projects aside that you are using well maintained dependencies?

Speaker 2

What is making it easy?

Speaker 1

Yes.

Speaker 2

Documentation.

Speaker 1

Documentation. Yeah.

Speaker 2

The documentation and you will find many tutorials, blog posts on how to use it, if there is an issue, how to fix it, how to tweak certain things with certain libraries that you need to do. Like some libraries also work with other libraries. It's not that I included this library, but that library is also included on other 10 libraries. So it's a dependency chain of libraries that nothing is independent. Everything is dependent on certain other libraries also. So while including, you also need to check. Whatever you are including, does it unnecessary like pulling other hundreds of things that you don't need? So that will slow down your application because your application is going to load that library in the production when you are running the application. So adding unnecessary, there are many things that you will check that do we really need just for one functionality or pulling out 100 things into the project, but write it by yourself or find some other library which is not having that many functionalities that we need. We don't need. Okay.

Speaker 1

Do you have any recommendations? security wise on dependence management to other developers.

Speaker 2

Any suggestion? Security wise like follow the regular guidelines which are there. You'll find it on internet. And if you are not sure like what are the security things that you should aware of. So I would say get the knowledge of that particular list first because you know by default it is in our head. We never think explicitly like okay when security means these hundred things we need to follow. you automatically follow it because you know it like by writing, okay, this is not right, this is the correct way. And so one has to take a good read on different blog posts, updates, what are the new things are happening. I will say that keep yourself updated.

Speaker 1

All right. I think that's all from me. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

Yes, thank you.

Speaker 1

I'll stop recording.